

Research Of Efficiency Of Use Of Production Capacity At The Enterprises Of Textile Industry On The Basis Of Methods Of Multivariate Statistical Analysis: On The Example Of Namangan Region Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan

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Abstract--- This article presents the results of the study of the efficiency of the use of production capacity in the textile industry of the Namangan region of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the methods of multidimensional statistical analysis. The article is divided into several parts, and the introduction justifies the relevance and demand of the conducted study, shows the compliance of the study with the priority direction of development of science and technology of the republic, reveals the scientific and practical significance of the obtained results, the introduction into practice of the results of the study. According to the authors, the efficiency of managing the use of production capacities in the textile industry is interpreted as an effort to organize their maximum use by assessing the degree of equal employment of technologies in existing production volumes or accepted capacities. The research carried out by the authors allowed to reveal the essence of the process of organization of efficient use of production capacities as a combined interrelated types of mechanisms and methods, which determine the conditions of rational combination of types of activities with organizational and managerial character, production facilities, production space, technologies and use of labor resources, the implementation of which will contribute to fulfillment of consumer requirements to the assortment, quantity and quality of produced products. The authors propose an algorithm for carrying out a study of production capacities selected using a cluster analysis method as the main object of the study on the basis of systematized factors characterizing the state of production capacity use. This technique is universal and can be used in the study of the efficiency of industrial production capacity utilization at the meso level.

Keywords--- production capacities, efficiency of use of production capacities, iterative application, cluster analysis, Ward's method, the k-average method.

Introduction

In Uzbekistan, light industry is an important sector of the economy that largely determines the country's production potential and competitiveness. Currently, about 12,000 large and small enterprises, as well as more than 500 joint ventures in light industry are operating effectively in Uzbekistan. These include the textile, spinning, sewing, knitting and silk industries, with a total workforce of over 150,000 people. At the same time, Uzbekistan's share in world exports of textile and sewing and knitwear products is only 0.3 percent. [1] Therefore, in modern conditions, there is a need to increase the use of the potential of enterprises operating in the industry based on modern methods of managing the use of production facilities. The Strategy for Action on five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 defines such priority tasks as "further modernization and diversification of industry by moving it to a qualitatively new level, aimed at the advanced development of high-tech manufacturing industries, primarily the production of finished products with high added value based on deep

processing of local raw materials". [2] Effective performance of these tasks requires accelerating the development of scientific and practical recommendations to improve the efficiency of management of production facilities at textile enterprises.

Scientifically grounded management of productive capacity of the enterprises of the textile industry demands working out of theoretical and methodical positions on the development of indicators of management of productive capacity of the enterprises on the basis of use of modern methods of the multidimensional mathematical-statistical analysis and imitating modeling.

For this study from the arsenal of methods of multivariate statistical analysis, the authors chose methods of cluster analysis, which allowed to implement an approach that has a scientific novelty. Its essence is that the initial stage of research of efficiency of use of industrial capacities at the enterprises should be divided into homogeneous groups on the volume indicators characterizing factors and results of the use of industrial capacities. This will make it possible to carry out an analysis that takes into account not only the difference in scale of enterprises' activities but also the peculiarities of their economic behavior due to this difference in scale.

The article is devoted to the use of cluster analysis algorithms to identify and characterize the current state of heterogeneity of textile industry enterprises in Uzbekistan on the indicators that determine the efficiency of production capacity utilization. On this basis, the authors have identified the main clusters of enterprises, which are qualitatively unique types in terms of set and impact of factors determining the efficiency of production capacity utilization. This approach is a prerequisite for the development of relevant capacity management indicators for textile industry enterprises, which cannot be the same for all enterprises but must be consistent with the types of enterprises identified by the authors of the article.

Literature Review

Many foreign scientists, such as F. Robert Jacobs [3], Richard B Chase, Mboya J. [4], Cline W. [5], Doeringer P. [6], Crean S., Dickerson K.G. [7], Nordas H. K., Verma S.[8], Juyoung Lee[9], Xiajun A.[10], Dorothe'e H., Mayukh D. conducted research and development on management, specialization and optimization of production capacities at textile enterprises.

In the CIS countries in this direction, scientific researches were carried out by such scientists, as M.S. Abryutina [11], A.I. Belov, G.N. Dobrin, A.E. Karlik, M.I. Bukhalkov [12], V.N. Vasiliev [13], O.S. Vihanskii [14], A.I. Naumov, M.V. Dadalova [15], A.Tikhomirova [26] and E.Matrosova.

The questions of management of the use of production capacities of textile enterprises in Uzbekistan and planning in regions are studied by academicians Ziyadullaev N.S.[16], Iskandarov I.I.; some aspects of management of the production process at textile enterprises have been studied by such scientists-economists as Khodiev B.Yu. [17], Bekmurodov A.Sh. [18], Boltabaev M.R. [19], Yuldoshev N.Q. [20], Shodmonova U.A. [21], Zakhidov G.E., Muratov R.S. [22], Tillyakhodzhaev A.A. [23], Khakimov Z.A. [24], and others, in scientific papers by Yusupov S.Sh. [25], Tursunov B.[27] and other scientists.

Despite the significant contribution of the listed scientists to science management, so far there has not been developed a common point of view on the definition of the essence of production facilities, not formed a methodological basis for the analysis of its reserves, not investigated comprehensive approaches to the formation and support of conditions for the effective use of production facilities, not identified priority areas of organizational changes associated with the instability of the external environment of the enterprise. Therefore, carrying out researches on the perfection of theoretical and methodical bases of the organization of effective use of capacities is expedient.

Methods And Data Collection

As of January 1, 2018, 1144 textile enterprises have been operated in Namangan region On the basis of the selective analysis the authors of the article have collected statistical data on 60 enterprises of the textile industry including representativeness. The cluster analysis method was used in the article, which allows to distribute these enterprises into homogeneous groups on the complex analysis. Besides, for the subsequent estimation of "density" of the selected clusters, the iterative algorithm of the k-means method was used, which is based on minimization of dispersion within each cluster. As a result of a combination of the results of clustering by Ward method and iterative

application of the k-average method, the composition of cluster-forming variables of textile enterprises in the Namangan region on the indicators that determine the efficiency of production capacity utilization was determined.

Analysis And Results

4.1. Information basis for the grouping of textile industry enterprises in Uzbekistan by indicators characterizing the efficiency of production capacity utilization.

Based on generalization by the authors of the article, the data on 60 enterprises of the textile industry of Uzbekistan for 2015 - 2017 were carried out cluster analysis, which allows classifying these enterprises into homogeneous groups on a set of effective and factor indicators of efficiency of production facilities. The purpose of this stage of the study was to solve two problems:

1) to obtain for the period under review a comparative assessment of the distribution of the enterprises under study into homogeneous groups on the basis of a set of effective and factor indicators of efficiency of production facilities utilization. This is necessary to obtain conclusions about changes in the degree of differentiation of textile production sector in Uzbekistan, and, accordingly, about changes in the level of competition of textile producers from the standpoint of provision with production capacities and their efficiency; [28]

2) divide the enterprises of textile industry of Uzbekistan into separate types in terms of efficiency of use of production capacities and peculiarities of its factor support.

To solve the first problem, the so-called "agglomeration" methods of cluster analysis were applied, which allow to obtain groups of enterprises with minimal intra-group dispersion by the variables under consideration. Calculations were carried out using the STATISTICA 8.0 software package with the use of Ward's method and estimations of similarity of objects on the basis of Euclidean distances.[28]

As the initial indicators for the calculations were used indicators of the number, composition and movement of the labor force of enterprises, the composition and movement of fixed assets, indicators of the turnover of production inventories, production and sales volumes, financial results of enterprises.

The algorithms proposed by the authors for calculating the effective indicators of production capacity of textile industry enterprises in Uzbekistan are given below.

Initial results of clustering of enterprises are presented in Pic.1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Dendrogram of distribution of textile industry enterprises of Uzbekistan into clusters by productive and factor indicators of production capacity utilization, 2015.

Source: Author's calculations in Statistica 9.0

Fig.2. Dendrogram of the distribution of textile industry enterprises in Uzbekistan into clusters on productive and factor indicators of capacity utilization, 2017.

Source: author's calculations in Statistica 9.0 program.

As follows from the data in Figures 1 and 2, between 2015 and 2017, significant structural shifts took place in the distribution of textile industry enterprises in Uzbekistan. (Annex 1)

In 2015, the enterprises under consideration were clearly divided into two clusters in terms of the indicators presented above: the first cluster (about 2/3 of the total number) included more homogeneous enterprises (it is marked by a light green oval); the second cluster (about 1/3 of the total number) was also homogeneous, but to a lesser extent, enterprises (marked by a dark green oval). [28]

Common characteristics of the textile industry this year: it is represented by two sectors of enterprises, each of which contained quite similar (homogeneous) enterprises in multidimensional evaluation by factor and performance indicators of production capacity utilization;

By 2017, there was a group of special (heterogeneous with respect to the rest) enterprises in the industry, which became much more different in terms of quantitative characteristics of factors and results of efficiency in the use of production facilities, but at the same time, the distribution of the other enterprises into two groups became more uniform. [28]

Thus, over the period under consideration, the heterogeneity of the composition of enterprises in the textile industry of Uzbekistan increased in terms of volume quantitative parameters of the efficiency of the use of production facilities: at the same time, an insignificant group of significantly different enterprises in terms of number (less than 10%) was distinguished.

4.2. the k-average method in identifying indicators that determine the differentiation of textile industry enterprises in Uzbekistan by the characteristics of efficiency of production capacity utilization.

The second of the above tasks was solved based on the k-average method.

The iteration algorithm of the k-average method used in the study is based on minimizing dispersion within each cluster. This criterion - a prerequisite for the subsequent assessment of the "density" of the selected clusters.

As a result of a combination of the results of clustering by Ward method and iterative application of k-average method was determined the composition of cluster-forming variables of textile enterprises in Uzbekistan on the indicators that determine the efficiency of production capacity utilization (Table).

Table 1.

The final composition of cluster-forming variables that determine the efficiency of use of production capacities of enterprises of the textile industry of Republic of Uzbekistan developed based on the method k-average, 2017.

Variable name	
Net revenue from sales of products (goods, works and services)	
Cost of products sold (goods, works and services)	Total
	Including production costs
	Period Expenses
	Other Expenses
	depreciation of property, plant and equipment and intangible assets
Profit (loss (-)) before income tax payment	
Income tax, other taxes and other mandatory payments from profit	
Net profit (loss (-))	
Production stocks at the beginning of the year	Total

Production stocks at the end of the year	Total
Production stocks	Finished products at beginning of the year
	Finished products at the end of year
	Products at the beginning of the year
Cost of fixed assets at initial (replacement) value at year-end	
Amount of depreciation of fixed assets at the beginning of the year	
Production Volume of industrial products (works, services) in actual prices (without VAT and excise tax)	
The production cost of manufactured products (goods, works and services)	
The volume of goods, works and services performed in-house (without VAT and excise tax)	

4.3. Algorithm for evaluation of production capacity utilization efficiency and identification of main reasons for differentiation of textile industry enterprises of Uzbekistan by characteristics of production capacity utilization

For an estimation of indicators of efficiency of use of industrial capacity on the basis of the list of the initial data presented above, the authors have developed the following algorithm consisting of 4 stages:

1. Aggregate indicator of production activity result is determined (evaluation of added value as a sum of wage fund indicator, profit (loss (-) before profit tax payment, depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets).

In accordance with the symbols of the variables adopted in Table 5 (Section 1), this stage of calculation can be written down:

$$DS = V104+V219+V211$$

2) Value added is calculated on the basis of one replaced job (average annual number of employees (including external part-time employees as well as persons who performed work under contracts of a civil law nature, converted to full-time equivalent):

$$LS_{RM} = LS/V143$$

Based on the fact that the textile industry is a labor-intensive industry and due to limited input data, this indicator is used to assess the production capacity of enterprises by its imputing two variants of the maximum value:

A) the group maximum (DS_{ZM_GR}), i.e. the maximum value set for a selected group of enterprises based on the results of cluster analysis (see Section 1);

B) by the industry maximum (DS_{ZM_HRM}) - by the value obtained for the "leader" of the industry - the enterprise "NAMANGAN MOMIQ SOCHIQLARI".

3. The index of production capacity at the enterprises of textile industry is calculated as a product of the index of "imputation" (potentially possible return of the added value on one replaced workplace at the given group of enterprises and/or at the branch as a whole) and the actual average annual number of employees at the given enterprise (including external part-time workers, and also the persons who carried out works under contracts of civil-law character, in recalculation on full employment equivalent) [28]:

A) based on group potential:

$$PM_{gr} = (DS_{ZM_GR}) * V143$$

B) based on sectoral potential:

$$PM_{otr} = (DS_ZM_OTR) * V143$$

4. The indicator of the efficiency of use of production capacity in relation is calculated:

A) to group capacity:

$$Ef/gr = (DS / PMg) * 100$$

B) to sectoral potential:

$$Ef/off = (DS / PM_{ot}) * 100$$

The algorithm proposed above was tested separately for each group of enterprises in the textile industry, separated by the results of cluster analysis. The following results have been obtained:

1. For the **first group of enterprises** (5) "with the most critical state of production" in the assessment of **volume indicators**, characterizing the efficiency of production capacity utilization, the results are presented in Table 1.

As it follows from the final data of Table 1 (columns 9-10), as well as their presentation in Fig.1, the highest indicator of production capacity utilization efficiency **among the enterprises of the 1st group** was observed at the enterprise "UZTEX UCHKURGAN" [28] (100% in relation to the group maximum), the lowest - at the enterprise "GOLDEN SILK" (37, 14%). As a whole on the given group of enterprises efficiency of use of industrial capacity as compared to the maximum potential on the given group made 52,56 %.

Fig.1. Estimated values of production capacity utilization efficiency indicators among the enterprises of the first group were observed at "UZTEX UCHKURGAN", the lowest - at "GOLDEN SILK", 2017, %.

Note: the blue color represents the results of the assessment of the efficiency of production capacity utilization in relation to the group potential of production per one replaced workplace; brown color represents the results of the assessment of the efficiency of production capacity utilization in relation to the sectoral potential of production.

Source: author's calculations in Statistica 9.0.

Calculation of indicators of efficiency of production capacity utilization on the first and the second group of enterprises of textile industry of Namangan region were made in Excel, and only results of calculations are given in the article.

In general, on the given group of the enterprises, the indicator of the efficiency of use of industrial capacities has been made in Excel, and in the article, only results of calculations are given.

2. For the **second group of enterprises** (54) defined by the results of cluster analysis as statistically homogeneous on the basis of evaluation by volumetric indicators characterizing efficiency of production capacity utilization, the results are presented in Table 2.

The general group indicator of the efficiency of use of industrial capacity (concerning the maximum potential on this group) has made 4,32 %. At the same time, it ranges from a local minimum of 2.0 % (enterprise "SHAF") to a local maximum of 100 % (enterprise "ATLASMEN").

From the comparison of the results obtained separately for the first and second groups of enterprises, it can be concluded that although the first group differs significantly lower volume values of indicators characterizing the resources (and results) of the use of production capacity, these indicators are more "balanced", which leads to a higher intragroup efficiency of the use of production capacity than the enterprises of the second group.

Comparison of the enterprises of textile industry of Uzbekistan in terms of efficiency of production capacity utilization should be carried out on the basis of comparable efficiency indicator, calculated in relation to the sectoral maximum of production potential (on the basis of consolidation of data presented in the tables 1 and 2, tables 10). For a more visual presentation, 10 enterprises, which are in the "Top 10" ranked series on the values of the production capacity utilization efficiency indicator, are highlighted in Figure 2. As follows from the data in Fig.2, the leaders of the industry on a comparable performance indicator are enterprises "NAMANGAN MOMIQ SOCHIQLARI", "ATLASMEN", "DO'STLIKA".

Fig.2. Distribution of "Top 10" enterprises-leaders of textile industry of Uzbekistan on the indicator of production capacity utilization efficiency, %, 2018.

Note: green color indicates the industry maximum.

Source: author's calculations in Statistica 9.0.

As a whole, the distribution of the aggregate of enterprises of the textile industry of Uzbekistan on the calculated values of the efficiency index of the use of production capacity is asymmetrical (the median is less than the average level, which corresponds to the right-hand asymmetry).

Fig.3. Estimation of conformity to the exponential law of distribution of textile industry enterprises of Uzbekistan on the calculated value of the efficiency index of production capacity utilization, %, 2017.

The asymmetry is quite significant because according to Fig.3, this distribution at a high level of significance corresponds to the exponential law of distribution (confirmed by Chi-square criterion). This indicates a rapid "leap" up the number of enterprises with the lowest level of efficiency in the use of production capacity relative to the number of enterprises with its maximum level.[28]

Conclusions

The carried out studies have led to the following conclusions:

- 1) Comparative analysis of the capacity utilization efficiency carried out for the development of management decisions should be carried out for comparable enterprises within a homogeneous group (cluster) if the necessary information is available;
- 2) Five enterprises with the most critical state of production in terms of capacity utilization efficiency have been identified.

"GOLDEN SILK" PE
LLC "UCHQURGAN TEXTILE" JV
"UZTEX UCHKURGAN" LLC
LLC "TOSHBULOQ-TEKS" JV
LLC "AISHA HOME TEXTILE" JV

3) The main "mass" - 54 enterprises form a homogeneous group in terms of factor and efficiency characteristics of production capacity utilization. They can be compared in order to identify specific conditions and factors providing differentiation of production capacity utilization efficiency.

Thus, the "stratification" of the set of enterprises in the textile industry of the Namangan region is primarily due to the worsening of the situation at the enterprises with low efficiency as compared with the total set of enterprises in this sector. The obtained quantitative and substantial results can serve as a basis for the specification of the simulation model developed for control over the efficiency of use at the enterprises of the textile industry of Uzbekistan.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the research results:

1. Capacity utilization efficiency at the textile industry enterprises of Uzbekistan is determined to a lesser extent by the volume indicators of resources and results of production activities, and to a greater extent - by their balance,
2. The distribution of enterprises in the textile industry of Uzbekistan on the calculated values of the efficiency indicator of the use of production capacity is very asymmetrical, corresponds to the exponential law of distribution.
3. The identified enterprises, which are part of the groups of "leaders" and "outsiders" on a comparable indicator of the efficiency of production capacity utilization, should be analyzed in detail to determine the reasons for their "special" position in the industry.
4. The obtained results should be taken into account in the specification of the simulation multifactor model of production capacity utilization efficiency by the textile industry of Uzbekistan.

Further research may include the construction of an imitation model of production capacity utilization efficiency, which can be defined as a logical and mathematical description of the dependence of the level of production capacity utilization factor of the enterprise on the combination of factors determining it, the nature of their interdependence, the form and force of influence on the modeled value.

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- [28] <http://gik.mu.edu.tr/en>

Appendix

№	Company name	Address and telephone
1	NORINTEKS AJ	Namangan region, Narindistrict
2	"SHOXIDON" PC	Namangan region, Turakurgandistrict
3	"UYCHI TONGI" PC	Namangan region, Uychidistrict
4	"MIKOIL MURSALIN" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
5	"RAYHON TOLA" LLC	Namangan region, Narindistrict
6	"USTA MAJIDXON" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
7	"KOSONSOY IPYIGIRUV NOTO'QIMA" LLC	Namangan region, Kasandistrict
8	"MARJON TOLA FAYZ" LLC	Namangan region Namangan city

9	"CHORTOQ SAHOVAT MEHR MURUVVAT" LLC	Namangan region, Charta district
10	"GOLDEN SILK" BE	Namangan region, Namangan city
11	"MEGA TEKSTIL" LLC BPC	Namangan region, Uychi district
12	"LORDGEN BIZNES" LLC	Namangan region, Narin district
13	"YORKATAY TO'QIMACHI" LLC	Namangan region, Uychi district
14	"KOSONSOY TUQIMACHI" LLC	Namangan region, Kosan district
15	"UYCHI-TEKS" LLC	Namangan region, Uychi district
16	"TEKS DEBO SABOT" LLC	Namangan region, Chust district
17	"YANGI OBOD KELAJAK SERVIS" LLC	Namangan region, Chust district
18	LLC "UCHQURGAN TEXTILE" JV	Namangan region, Uchqurgan district
19	"UZTEX UCHKURGAN" LLC	Namangan region, Uchqurgan district
20	"NAMANGAN O'QUV ISHLAB CHIQRISH" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan district
21	"401 XMMKK" LLC	Namangan region, Narin district
22	"KAMOL MED FARM" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
23	"SHAF" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
24	"ATLASMEN" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
25	"FAYZ SERVIS UI" LLC	Namangan region, Narin district
26	"B QIRG'IZOV" LLC	Namangan region, Uychi district
27	"MUHAMMADXON" PC	Namangan region, Namangan city
28	"DO'STLIK A" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
29	"BUNYOD" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
30	"UYCHI NOTO'QIMA MATO" LLC	Namangan region, Uychi district
31	"MUAZZAM TEXTILE" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
32	"TURON-95 MBI" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
33	"Namangan tukimachi" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
34	LLC "TOSHBULOQ-TEKS" JV	Namangan region, Namangan district
35	"EAGLE INTERNATIONAL TEX" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
36	"ОРИФ АКРАМ СЕРВИС" PC	Namangan region, Namangan city
37	"CHOSHOH" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
38	"ZUMAR" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
39	"TEKNOLOG-GR" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
40	"NAMIMPEKS TEKSTIL" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
41	"TUBO TEXTILE" XSI LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
42	"LYUKS PLYUS SERVIS" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
43	"ISTIQLOL TEKSTIL DIZAYN" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
44	"KUSHON ZILOL SUV JAVOHIRI" LLC	Namangan region, Kosan district
45	"BARKAS-TEKS" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
46	"TUQIMACHI SANOAT TEKSTIL" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
47	"NAM TEX" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
48	"A'ZAM TEKS SAVDO SERVIS" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
49	"NAMANGAN MOMIQ SOCHIQLARI" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
50	"ALI TEKSTIL GRAND SERVIS" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
51	LLC "AISHA HOME TEXTILE" JV	Namangan region, Namangan city
52	"GABON TEXTILE" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
53	"AZIZ-FAYZ-TO'QIMACHI" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
54	"TERRY JAR TEXTILE" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
55	"JAR KUSHON TEKSTIL" PC	Namangan region, Kosan district

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56	"GULOBOD TEKS" LLC	Namangan region, Namangan city
57	"MIRAZIZ OBOD GUZARI" PC	Namangan region, Namangan city
58	"MA'RIFAT SAVDO SANOAT" PC	Namangan region, Namangan city
59	"AKBAR-VODIYSI" PC	Namangan region, Namangan city
60	"XADICHABONU TEKSTIL SERVIS" PC	Namangan region, Namangan city